

Saturation Protection for Feedback Linearizable Systems using Sliding Mode Theory

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Abstract

It is shown that sliding mode control is equivalent to feedback linearization with an appropriate choice of desired output dynamics. It is this equivalence that leads to the development of a control command limiting algorithm that provides actuator saturation protection for input/output feedback linearizable systems with more inputs than outputs. The command limiting algorithm is integrated with an optimal control redundancy algorithm to form a complete control allocation method. The control allocation minimizes control effector deflections for control redundant situations and limits control commands for control deficient situations. The control allocation method is applied to a tailless fighter aircraft model.

1 Introduction

Actuator limit and integrator windup protection are typically approached either from a single-input, single-output (SISO) point of view [1] that ignore directionality or multi-input, multi-output (MIMO) points of view that maintain control direction [2, 3, 4, 5]. Ignoring directionality may have potentially dire consequences for highly unstable MIMO systems. Maintaining command direction has been shown to provide graceful degradation in some cases [2, 4], while other efforts have shown that performance degradation may be premature while maintaining command direction [6]. An attempt has been made in this paper to develop a structure that provides more control of performance degradation during control deficient situations.

2 Tracking Control

This section considers robust tracking for a class of dynamical systems. A canonical form is developed that facilitates analysis of feedback linearizable dynamical systems with more control effectors than commanded variables. The concept of control allocation is reviewed, and

conditions are developed that provide equivalence between feedback linearization and sliding mode control.

2.1 Feedback Linearizable Systems

Consider dynamical systems represented by ordinary differential equations affine in the control

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{x} &= f(x) + g(x)u \\ y &= h(x) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where $x \in \mathbb{R}^{n_x}$ is the state, $u \in \mathbb{R}^m$ is the control input, $y \in \mathbb{R}^{n_y}$ are the commanded variables, and $f(x)$, columns of $g(x)$, and $h(x)$ are smooth vector fields on \mathbb{R}^n . It is assumed that there are at least as many controls as commanded variables, i.e. $m \geq n_y$. It is assumed that the system in eq.(1) has a well-defined vector relative degree $\{r_1, \dots, r_{n_y}\}$. Therefore, there always exists a diffeomorphic state transformation to the following canonical form

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{z} \\ \dot{\psi} \\ \dot{w} \end{bmatrix} &= \begin{bmatrix} f_z(z, \psi, w) \\ A_\psi \psi + A_w w \\ f_w(z, \psi, w) \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} g_z(z, \psi, w) \\ 0 \\ g_w(z, \psi, w) \end{bmatrix} u \\ \psi &= [\psi_1^T \ \dots \ \psi_{n_y}^T]^T \\ \psi_i &= [y_i \ \dots \ y_i^{(r_i-2)}]^T \\ w &= [y_1^{(r_1-1)} \ \dots \ y_{n_y}^{(r_{n_y}-1)}]^T \\ y_i^{(k)} &= \frac{d^k y_i}{dt^k} \\ A_\psi &= \text{diag} \{A_{\psi_1}, \dots, A_{\psi_{n_y}}\} \\ A_{\psi_i} &= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ \vdots & \dots & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{(r_i-1) \times (r_i-1)} \\ A_w &= \text{diag} \{A_{w_1}, \dots, A_{w_{n_y}}\} \\ A_{w_i} &= [0 \ \dots \ 0 \ 1]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{(r_i-1)} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where z are the uncommanded states, ψ are the kinematic commanded states, and w are the kinetic com-

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manded states. A well-defined vector relative degree implies that time derivatives of all kinetic commanded states are affected by at least one control and that g_w has rank = n_y . It is further assumed that each control affects at least one kinetic commanded state time derivative.

It is assumed that the system in eq.(2) is minimum phase defined as the asymptotic stability of the following zero dynamics

$$\dot{z} = f_z(z, 0, 0) + g_z(z, 0, 0)\tilde{u}(z) \quad (3)$$

where $\tilde{u}(z)$ is the control that maintains zero commanded states

$$\tilde{u}(z) = \{u | f_w(z, 0, 0) + g_w(z, 0, 0)u = 0\} . \quad (4)$$

2.2 Minimal Control Dimension

Square systems are those which have an equal number of controls and commanded variables, while control redundancy implies more controls than commanded variables. This section defines a design procedure for minimizing the control dimension of the minimum phase control redundant system given in eq.(2).

The dimension of the controls may be minimized by defining the product of the controls and the kinetic commanded state control effectiveness as the minimum dimension control or generalized control, d_w

$$d_w \equiv g_w(z, \psi, w)u \quad (5)$$

which results in the following square system for design

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{z} \\ \dot{\psi} \\ \dot{w} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_z(z, \psi, w) + g_z(z, \psi, w)\rho(d_w) \\ A_\psi\psi + A_w w \\ f_w(z, \psi, w) + d_w \end{bmatrix} . \quad (6)$$

The control design philosophy is that a feedback controller is designed for the square system in eq.(6) in terms of a generalized control command, d_w^c . This generalized control command is mapped to the actual control commands by the control allocation function $\rho(d_w)$ such that the following is satisfied

$$g_w(z, \psi, w)\rho(d_w^c) = d_w^c . \quad (7)$$

Alternatively, the solution to the following constrained optimization problem provides the mapping from generalized to actual control commands

$$\min_u J = F(u) \text{ subject to } g_w(z, \psi, w)u = d_w^c . \quad (8)$$

Constrained optimization naturally addresses the control redundancy and allows the flexibility of additional constraints such as actuator limits.

2.3 Feedback Linearizing Control

The robust tracking problem is to design an input to state stabilizing feedback control law [7] that provides asymptotic tracking of a given command profile $y_c(t)$

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow \infty} |y_c(t) - y(t)| = 0 . \quad (9)$$

The controller should provide stabilization and tracking in the presence of unknown disturbances, noise and model parameters.

The feedback linearization control solution to the robust tracking problem for the system in eq.(6) is given by the following

$$d_w^{fl} = -\hat{f}_w(z, \psi, w) + v(\psi, w, y_c, y_c^{(1)}, \dots) \quad (10)$$

where \hat{f}_w is an estimate of f_w and v is a robust tracking controller for the following command variable subsystem

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\psi} \\ \dot{w} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_\psi\psi + A_w w \\ v(\psi, w, y_c, y_c^{(1)}, \dots) + f_w - \hat{f}_w \end{bmatrix} . \quad (11)$$

The function v is often referred to as the augmented or desired command variable dynamics.

2.4 Sliding Mode Control

A sliding mode control solution to the robust tracking problem is given by the following control vector elements

$$\begin{aligned} d_{w_i}^{sm} &= y_{c_i}^{(r_i)} - \hat{f}_{w_i}(z, \psi, w) + \\ & c_{2,i}e_i^{(r_i-1)} + \dots + c_{r_i+1,i}e_i^{(0)} + k_i \text{sgn}(\sigma_i) \\ \sigma_i &\equiv e_i^{(r_i-1)} + c_{2,i}e_i^{(r_i-2)} + \dots + c_{r_i,i}e_i^{(0)} + \\ & + c_{r_i+1,i}x_{e_i} \\ \dot{x}_{e_i} &= e_i \\ e_i &\equiv y_{c_i} - y_i . \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The manifold $\sigma = 0$ represents the desired output tracking error performance of the nonlinear system in eq.(2).

It is interesting to note that the feedback linearization and sliding mode control laws are equivalent if the feedback linearization desired dynamics are chosen to have the following vector elements

$$\begin{aligned} v_i &= k_i \text{sgn}(\sigma_i) + y_{c_i}^{(r_i)} \\ & + c_{2,i}e_i^{(r_i-1)} + \dots + c_{r_i+1,i}e_i^{(0)} . \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The following sliding mode control perspective will provide interesting insight for command limiting of feedback linearization controllers to prevent actuator saturation.

Sliding mode control motion may be interpreted as occurring in two phases, reaching and sliding. The two phase interpretation is valid since the system state is guaranteed to reach the sliding manifold in finite time. The sliding mode is defined as motion on the manifold

$\sigma = 0$. Sliding motion is governed by the sliding control d_w^{slide} whose elements are defined by the following

$$d_{w_i}^{slide} \equiv d_{w_i}^{sm}|_{\sigma=0} = y_{c_i}^{(r_i)} - \hat{f}_{w_i}(z, \psi, w) + c_{2,i}e_i^{(r_i-1)} + \dots + c_{r_i+1,i}e_i^{(0)}. \quad (14)$$

The reaching phase is essentially the motion while not in the sliding mode, i.e. $\sigma \neq 0$. The reaching phase motion is governed by the discontinuous control d_w^{reach} whose elements are defined by the following

$$d_{w_i}^{reach} \equiv k_i \text{sgn}(\sigma_i). \quad (15)$$

Undesirable control chattering may occur due to the discontinuity in $d_{w_i}^{reach}$. The chattering may be eliminated by replacing the signum function with a saturation function at the expense of decreased robustness and loss of finite reaching time to the sliding manifold. Considering only the linear region of the saturation function, the reaching control vector elements become

$$d_{w_i}^{reach} = k_i \sigma_i \quad (16)$$

and the corresponding desired dynamics in the feedback linearization framework are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{v}_i &= y_{c_i}^{(r_i)} + (c_{2,i} + k_i)e_i^{(r_i-1)} \\ &+ \dots + (c_{r_i+1,i} + k_i c_{r_i,i})e_i^{(0)} \\ &+ k_i c_{r_i+1,i} x_{e_i} \\ \dot{x}_{e_i} &= e_i. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

For this continuous or smooth sliding mode control formulation, the sliding and reaching phases are conceptual since the sliding manifold is no longer reached in finite time. Sliding is motion "near" the sliding manifold, and reaching is motion "far" from the sliding manifold. These concepts become useful for a proposed command limiting algorithm that protects actuators from saturation.

3 Nonlinear Dynamic Actuators

Typically actuator dynamical models are neglected for feedback compensation design if the actuator bandwidth is well beyond the desired open loop system bandwidth. Actuator position and rate limits are not directly accounted for in linear design methods due to their nonlinear nature. This problem may be indirectly solved by treating the nonlinearities as uncertainties for robust control design. However, the closed loop response to small commands (those within a linear region of the input nonlinearity) may suffer considerably.

An alternative is to design a control allocator that limit generalized control commands to account for actuator limits and optimize large command performance.

This approach has the advantage that the small command performance will not suffer. Digital implementation of the controller and a discretized actuator model provide the framework to develop a control allocator that computes actuator commands that do not violate actuator limits.

3.1 Control Command Limiting

Recall the control allocation problem in eq.(8). With neither actuator dynamics nor limits, there is always sufficient control power to satisfy the equality constraint, so this problem always has a feasible solution. However, actuator limits impose additional constraints on the control allocation problem that may render the optimization problem infeasible. The capability to relax problem constraints is necessary to always pose a feasible optimization problem. Since actuator limits are hardware limits, they may not be relaxed. Therefore, the control command equality constraint in eq.(8) is relaxed by limiting the generalized control command, d_w^c .

As suggested in [6], consider decomposing the commanded generalized control into a set of partitions

$$d_w^c = d_1 + d_2 + \dots + d_k \quad (18)$$

where it is assumed desirable to limit d_w^c , if necessary, by first limiting d_k , then d_{k-1} , and so on. This suggests a priority among the control law partitions. Note the partitions and the priority among partitions may not be obvious for all control laws. A priority based upon sliding mode control theory is developed in the next section as an extension to past work [6], but for now assume the partitions and the priority are given. The following constrained optimization extends the optimization in eq.(8) to account for control power deficiency due to actuator limits by providing constraint relaxation capability through generalized control command limiting

$$\min_{u, \lambda} J = F(u) - \sum_{j=1}^k \lambda_j \quad (19)$$

subject to

$$g_w(x, \psi, w)u = \lambda_1 d_1 + \lambda_2 d_2 + \dots + \lambda_k d_k$$

$$u_i \leq u_i \leq u_{u_i}$$

$$0 \leq \lambda_j \leq 1$$

$$\text{If } \lambda_j = 1 : \lambda_{j-1} = \lambda_{j-2} = \dots = 1$$

$$\text{If } \lambda_j = 0 : \lambda_{j+1} = \lambda_{j+2} = \dots = 0$$

$$\text{If } 0 < \lambda_j < 1 : \begin{cases} \lambda_{j-1} = \lambda_{j-2} = \dots = 1 \\ \lambda_{j+1} = \lambda_{j+2} = \dots = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$i = 1, \dots, m$$

$$j = 1, \dots, k$$

where u_l and u_u are vectors of control limits.

3.2 Dynamic Limiting Priority

A static control command priority was suggested in [6] that was based upon feedback linearization control law partition functionality, such as stability or decoupling. Although the static priority worked well for maneuvering flight without disturbances, it may not provide optimal solutions for other situations such as flight in turbulence or gusts. A dynamic priority is developed in this section based upon the sliding mode control perspective in Section 2.4.

Recall the two phase sliding mode controller interpretation: the reaching controller primarily affects motion far from the sliding manifold, and the sliding controller primarily affects motion when the system state is near the sliding manifold. It may be concluded that d_w^{slide} will have a small magnitude compared to d_w^{reach} during the reaching phase. Similarly, d_w^{reach} will have a small magnitude compared to d_w^{slide} during the sliding phase. However since the controller is a vector function, the magnitude and direction of each control part are equally important. For example, the direction of a small magnitude control part may be critical. Once either magnitude or direction is destroyed, the other may be meaningless. For control deficient situations such as actuator limiting, it may be desirable to maintain the direction and magnitude of one control partition while altering the other control part to satisfy actuator limits. So it is conjectured that a maximum number of unaltered control parts during limiting is preferable. This is accomplished by prioritizing the control parts such that the control part with the smallest magnitude has the highest priority and the control part with the largest magnitude has the lowest priority, i.e.

$$\|d_1\|_2 \leq \|d_2\|_2 \leq \dots \leq \|d_k\|_2. \quad (20)$$

Note that the priority of past work [6] may be consistent with the priority in eq.(20) at the onset of large maneuver commands without disturbances.

4 Flight Control Application

This section describes application of the dynamic control command priority to a tailless fighter aircraft [6, 8]. The tailless configuration includes eleven conventional and innovative control effectors that provide forces and moments in multiple axes.

The tailless aircraft rigid body inner loop flight control equations of motion may be placed in the form of eq.(2) with the following choices of commanded and uncommanded states

$$z = \begin{bmatrix} \alpha & \beta \end{bmatrix}, \quad \psi = \emptyset$$

$$w = y = \begin{bmatrix} P \cos \alpha + R \sin \alpha \\ K_\alpha \alpha + Q \\ K_\beta \beta - P \sin \alpha + R \cos \alpha \end{bmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

Note that for aircraft flight control the zero dynamics are typically asymptotically stable for the choice of variables given above. For aircraft, g_z is typically sufficiently small to maintain natural asymptotic stability of the zero dynamics.

The generalized control law is given by eq.(10) with the following desired dynamics chosen based upon robustness to historical levels of $f_w - \hat{f}_w$ uncertainty for this class of aircraft

$$v = (c_2 + k)e + kc_2x_e + k_{ff}y_c$$

$$c_2 = 2.5 \frac{\text{rad}}{\text{sec}}$$

$$k = 2.5 \frac{\text{rad}}{\text{sec}}$$

$$k_{ff} = -2.5 \frac{\text{rad}}{\text{sec}} \quad (22)$$

where k_{ff} is an additional feedforward gain to enhance handling qualities.

Consider the following generalized control partitions

$$d_a = -\hat{f}_w(z, \psi, w)$$

$$d_p = (c_2 + k)e$$

$$d_i = kc_2x_e$$

$$d_{ff} = k_{ff}y_c \quad (23)$$

where d_a is the decoupling/cascading or deaugmentation control, d_p is the proportional control, d_i is the integral control, and d_{ff} is the feedforward control. Since there are four control partitions, the dynamic priority of Section 3.2 implies the following relationship

$$\|d_1\|_2 \leq \|d_2\|_2 \leq \|d_3\|_2 \leq \|d_4\|_2. \quad (24)$$

Note that $d_1, d_2, d_3,$ and d_4 are chosen dynamically from the partitions in eq.(23) such that the relationship in eq.(24) holds.

4.1 Simulation Analysis

Simulation responses to simultaneous commands in roll (y_1) and pitch (y_2) are presented in this section to show the benefits of the prioritized control command limiting. The maneuver is similar to a loaded roll. The first case, indicated in Figs.(1) and (2) by *prior*, is the dynamic priority command limiting. For comparison, a command limiting algorithm that maintains the generalized control command direction by forcing $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \lambda_4$ [6] is indicated in Figs.(1) and (2) by *dir*. The command variable responses are shown in Fig.(1), and the scalings for unachievable commands are shown in Fig.(2). Note that d_w^c is unachievable at the onset of the commands as indicated by $\lambda_4 < 1$. Further, note the coupling of the roll response with the pitch and yaw response due to limiting commands to maintain command direction. However, the prioritized control command limiting only limits d_4 and d_3 which maintains desired decoupled responses.

5 Conclusions

It is shown that sliding mode control and feedback linearization are equivalent with the appropriate choice of desired dynamics. A dynamic generalized control command priority is developed for multi-input, multi-output feedback linearizable systems to provide actuator saturation protection through control command limiting. The dynamic priority is applied to a tailless fighter aircraft simulation, and the results show improved large command performance compared to a direction preservation command limiting approach.

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Figure 1: Command Variable Responses

Figure 2: λ Responses